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THE INSURANCE CULTURE OF MUSLIM TOURISTS

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Abstract

The current topic is dictated by the growing share of Muslim tourists in Europe and around the world. Their peculiarity is that they often travel without travel insurance. Most of them reject the possibility of insuring because it is contrary to their religion and cultural habits. On the one hand, this consumer anomaly is burdening tour operators and their partners, but on the other hand, it finds good market horizons for insurance companies. It is interesting to know the possible reasons why Muslims are risk seekers and resistant to insurance protection. The main root cause of the anomaly is the religious and moral principles of Sharia, which determine the specific consumer attitude toward insurance services. The solution is in favor of product innovation and integration of takaful insurance into the insurers' product range. Takaful requires the organization of the insurance business to be of a mutual type, which is fundamentally different from the prevailing shareholder type in the Western world. The potential for European and American insurers is enormous, given that takaful insurance provides them the opportunity to put themselves in new markets and to occupy unsatisfied market niches.

Key words: insurance culture, Islamic tourism, takaful insurance, mutual insurance business, insurance innovations, behavioral insurance

Muslim tourists and their insurance anomalies

The European tourism market is constantly changing, both in terms of its guest structure and its product diversity. One of the factors generating changes in tourist services is the growing number of Muslim tourists in European resorts. The countries of Europe and Central Asia when considered as a common group rank second, as an attractive tourist destination for them. At these destinations they spend about 25% of their tourism budgets. Moreover, the first country in the Global Index of Muslim Tourism is a European country located in the Balkans. Bosnia and Herzegovina has attracted the attention of this segment for 2017 as the friendliest territory¹. Other countries in Europe preferred by Muslims for excursions are Germany, Great Britain and France, which have earned \$8.3 billion in 2014 only (See Table 1). Their affinity with these countries of course, apart from everything else, is also related to the existence of relationships between travelers and emigrants in these places.

Table 1. Top 20 source markets for Islamic tourism, 2013-2014

Rank	Country	Size (US \$ Billion)	Rank	Country	Size (US \$ Billion)
1	Saudi Arabia	17,8	11	Germany	3,6
2	Iran	14,3	12	Egypt	2,8

¹ Global Muslim Travel Index (2017). <https://www.crescentrating.com>

3	United Arab Emirates	11,2	13	Azerbaijan	2,4
4	Qatar	7,8	14	United Kingdom	2,4
5	Kuwait	7,7	15	Singapore	2,3
6	Indonesia	7,5	16	France	2,3
7	Malaysia	5,7	17	Iraq	2,2
8	Russia	5,4	18	United States	2,0
9	Turkey	4,5	19	Morocco	2,0
10	Nigeria	4,4	20	Lebanon	1,9

Source: Organization of Islamic cooperation (2017). Strategic roadmap for development of Islamic tourism in OIC member countries, p. 8

Muslim tourists have specific needs and habits to which tour operators in Europe are forced to adapt. Among their leading requirements are the opportunity to consume "halal" foods and the availability of prayer spaces². But there is another challenge for them. Their Muslim guests do not have a high insurance culture that puts them in charge of managing their personal risks. A very small part of the tourists, especially those who have had links with the European and American insurance practices, take out travel insurance. The main reason for such imprudent behavior is rooted in the religious beliefs of Muslims that allow participation in insurance schemes, but only if they are non-profit-making. However, non-commercial insurance is not a popular practice neither in Europe nor in any country with a developed market economy that prevents its spread among the Muslim population. Moreover, because of the lack of insurance experience, Muslims cannot recognize the benefits of insurance services, including taking advantage of them.

The logic of the Muslims' illogical insurance behavior

Like any other tourist trip, the visit of Muslims across Europe hides its risks. These may relate to their health, travel, accommodation, luggage, available valuables, emerging legal cases, and many others. Despite their potential occurrence, few Muslim tourists make adequate insurance coverage. This consumer anomaly provokes the interest of researchers and analysts because it is the key to successful insurance market adaptation. The analytical toolkit of behavioral insurance makes it possible to study this anomaly through the prism of the cultural and religious specificities of tourists from the Middle and Far East and thus offer workable insurance solutions.

From a cardinal point of view, insurance protection does not play a significant role in Muslim life and culture because it conflicts with local religious dogmas. According to Islamic beliefs, everything is in the hands of God, including natural disasters, miseries in life, the risks of the social and political world, and so on. In this context, he is the only one that can protect people from the dangers of the environment and no one can resist own destiny. In fact, insurance principles do not contradict this dogma, as insurance is a follow-up (post-factum) and does not aim to "oppose" God's prescriptions. Insurance is nothing more than compensation for damages that have

² Dinar Standard (2015). <http://www.dinarstandard.com/>

already occurred and a way to restore the normal standard of injured persons. Regardless of the proposed interpretation, Muslims' stubborn mistrust of insurance services remains incomprehensible. That is why we can look at the anomaly from another point of view. It is possible for people to perceive the emerging damages as God's punishment, which should not be countered. Sufferings is their lesson and a signal to people to lead a more righteous life. There is no particular logic in that because the Sharia advocates that everyone should struggle with difficulties and resolve adversities by helping others. Obviously the "insurance-religion" conflict cannot be found here, but it is possible to work towards the literacy of the Muslim population for dropping some misconceptions.

The consumer anomaly of Muslim tourists can be much better substantiated by the markedly commercial nature of the insurance business. The commercialism is more confronted with their religious beliefs and is a serious hindrance to its popularization. The Sharia as a set of legal, moral and religious norms of Islam introduces too stringent business principles that are incompatible with the modern understanding of profitable insurance. Its main principle is the equality (respectively the proportionality) of the wealth distribution and the sharing of responsibility among participants in commercial transactions. According to the basic religious law people have to refrain from entering into transactions whose end results are uncertain and are subject to predetermined monetary obligations (interests, fees, commissions, etc.). It is clear from this that the insurance services offered in their traditional form do not meet the requirements of the Sharia. By definition insurance contracts are aleatory contracts and in this sense do not guarantee insurance indemnity to all. In addition, insurance companies and their clients are not equal. Moreover, insurers form a secure profit at the expense of the insured persons. There is no doubt that the current religious business dogmas are incompatible with the commercial (corporate) organization of the insurance business in the Western world and require reconsideration of the model.

Market adaptations to the Muslims' insurance habits

Coordinated efforts by local authorities and the insurance business are needed to increase insurance density and insurance penetration in Middle and Far East countries. Offering innovative insurance products in line with religious beliefs in the Islamic world will be beneficial not only to Muslim tourists and their tour operators but also to society as a whole. The penetration of travel insurance into the Muslim lives will have an additional effect as a catalyst on the economic development of the tourist market. Improving financial infrastructure in many of the Islamic countries in recent years has created new opportunities that have forced some insurance companies from Europe and the US to redefine their product profile. In order to enforce these markets, they began offering insurances based on the takaful concept. It implies that the insurance business should be built through mutual assistance and solidarity in the relationship between an insurer and an insured person. Therefore, their insurance product innovations focus on mutual risk management.

The mutual organization of insurance enables through mutual assistance, coordination and cooperation to reach the equality and lack of financial asymmetry between the partners. Of course minimum legal requirements will be needed for the number of partners in mutual insurers and their risk exposure to work the Law of large numbers as a leading insurance principle. All of them will finance the risk in the insured group without burdening each other with debts while at the same time they will be able to benefit from the accumulated common funds. Such an organization is in

line with the zakat concept of the Sharia which admires the association in the face of human suffering and accepts the collective support of the injured as a normal practice. Moreover, no one in the insured group will profit from the misfortune of the other. The amount of insurance premiums will depend on the occurrence of risk in the insured group rather than the greed of the shareholders and the management's desire for personal gains. The main differences between takaful insurances and conventional insurances can be found in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Key differences between takaful and conventional insurance

Source: Khan, 2013, p. 42

Establishing a mutual insurance business is just one side of the innovation process. The other side requires Muslim tourists to be informed and familiarized with insurance principles. In this regard insurers will need an aggressive marketing policy with a highly educational nature. The emphasis of marketing messages should be placed on the equality of participants in the mutual insurance business and the lack of predetermined returns for insurers. Only in this way the Muslims will be oriented in the right direction without this being perceived as usury-based exploitation. Forming a sense of "fair play" in them is the key element for signing an insurance contract.

It is well known that the Sharia forbids believers from betting money, incl. to participate in gambling. And although the due insurance indemnity depends on unavoidable (objective) risks Muslims perceive insurance as a type of participation in an uncertain outcome scheme. Even if insurers have a desire, they cannot pay off to all their clients at least because the redistributive function of the insurance business will not be able to work. This is precisely why paid insurance premiums are treated by Muslims as a net profit for the insurer's shareholders and a recognizable loss for insured persons. In order to overcome this misunderstanding, innovative takaful insurances include clauses providing for a partial premium refund at a low loss rate. Thus the behavioral anomaly of Muslims associated with their pursuit of equivalence of cash flows under the insurance scheme can be resolved. This is because insurers will

refund part of the paid premiums in the absence of damages and paid compensations for them. In this way insurance will be less like a gambling game. It is very important to note that the Muslims' desire for equivalence is mostly related to their religious beliefs and perceptions for the insurance business rather than budget constraints and lack of financial literacy.

The future development of innovative takaful insurance

Takaful insurances gain increasing popularity among the Muslim population. Although mutual insurance business in Europe and North America has a small market share it revives in many Middle and Far East countries. Such countries are Indonesia, Malaysia, Saudi Arabia and the United Arab Emirates (See Figure 2). Against this background Turkey is no exception but in this country commercial (stock) insurance has its deserved place. This can easily be argued with the secular nature of Turkish society and the liberal regime of Turkish law³. In addition, some of the insurances in Turkey have a mandatory nature which also creates the conditions for a higher insurance culture. Given the changed ethnic structure of some European countries and the consequences of the refugee wave it may be expected that the mutual insurance business will be modernized into a new successful model. Exactly such signs are found in the UK, France, Luxembourg, Switzerland and others⁴.

Figure 2. Insurance (takaful) penetration and density, 2016

Source: Middle East Global Advisors, 2016, p. 8

³ Guner Law Office (2009). Turkey: Insurance law in Turkey.

⁴ World Islamic Insurance Directory (2015). Ins. Communications Pte. Ltd.

Trends in offering takaful insurance to Muslim tourists by local and foreign companies are encouraging. Most countries in the Middle and Far East have the potential to double their insurance penetration and insurance density. One of the main reasons for the low values of these indicators about the Islamic countries is the misunderstanding of insurance business in the context of religious canons. In fact, insurances can be offered in such a way that they do not contradict the Sharia. Of course their adapted design should be explained to Muslim tourists so that they can travel safely around the world without any religious remorse.

From the supply point of view insurers will need to make greater efforts to better identify the needs of the Muslim population and to offer innovative products on this basis. The market is extremely dynamic and promising. Any delay on their part will divert them from its absorption and mastery. The takaful insurance market in Europe is virtually undeveloped and those who master it can gain a huge advantage⁵.

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